

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PSYCHO-SOCIAL COMPETENCE AND MENTAL HEALTH AMONG INDIGENOUS STUDENTS AT SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL IN TELANGANA

DR. VITTAL RATHOD ¹ | DR. GEETHA GOPINATH ² | DR. SRINIVAS GHODAM ³

¹ TRAINED GRADUATE TEACHER (TGT-ENGLISH), MJPTBCWREI SOCIETY, DOULTHABAD (BOYS) SCHOOL, KODANGAL, VIKARABAD DISTRICT, TELANGANA STATE, INDIA.

² ASSISTANT PROFESSOR, DEPT. OF EDUCATION & EDUCATION TECHNOLOGY, SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF HYDERABAD.

³ POST DOCTORAL RESEARCH SCHOLAR, DEPT. OF EDUCATION & EDUCATION TECHNOLOGY, SCHOOL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, UNIVERSITY OF HYDERABAD.

ABSTRACT:

The present paper is targeted to determine the relationship between psychosocial competence and mental health among Indigenous secondary schools at the secondary school level in Telangana State. Furthermore, this study was done with the help of a psychosocial competence scale developed by the Investigator and the mental health of Indigenous secondary school students using a standardized research tool by Sen Gupta and Arun Kumar (2007). The co-relational research method was adopted. The study was organized at Telangana Tribal Welfare Residential Schools (TTWREIS) and Telangana Tribal Ashrama Schools (TTAS). A total of 153 secondary school levels were identified, of which 35 Indigenous students were at the secondary school level. Here chosen, simple random sampling using the lottery method. The survey method was taken on for data collection. After analysis, Tribal Welfare Residential Schools have no difference in their level of psychosocial competence; however, Welfare Residential Schools have a higher mean than that Tribal Ashrama Schools. Girls and Boys have a significant difference in their psychosocial competence, i.e. Boys have a higher mean than that Girls with a significant difference. The results indicated an important relationship between the psychosocial competence & mental health of Indigenous students at the secondary school level. It was also discovered there exists no significant gender variance between the psychosocial competence & mental health of secondary School Indigenous Students. Although, slight gender differences have been found. The researcher also stated an Important relation between the main dimensions of psychosocial competence & certain mental health areas among Indigenous students at the secondary school level.

KEYWORDS:

PSYCHOSOCIAL COMPETENCE, MENTAL HEALTH, INDIGENOUS STUDENTS SECONDARY SCHOOL.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

6th November 2025

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

8th November 2025

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is the most important period in life. It bridges the gap between childhood and adulthood. So, mental and physical growth during this period determines a man's physique. It is a period of transition. People in this period are enthusiastic, energetic, benevolent, driven, and self-centred. During adolescence, they develop a sense of moral and personal values. Here they live in a technological world. They have more opportunities to explore. Although their abilities are still developing, they need to develop the ability to cope with emotions. Advanced skills must be acquired to solve problems. Essentially, young adults need to be highly motivated to lead successful lives.

Adolescents can shift moods rapidly, indecisive between confidence and distress. Emotional development reaches its maximum during adolescence. Therefore, in emotional

expression and experience, the adolescent pro highest peak. At no stage is the child as restless and emotionally troubled as in adolescence. He is too sensitive, explosive, and moody. This is why the period is often d as a period of stresses and strains. In this way, as Ross clarifies. It is not easy to put a check on emotions during adolescence. Emotions take their roots into sep time consciousness during adolescence, and self-respect and personal pride increase too much. Group loyalty and a good amount of social sense. They cease to be ego-centric, selfish and unsocial. Co childhood, they become interested in the opposite sex. The friendships are no longer nomi believe in making intimate friendships and attach him closely to a group. Peer groups are control the social behaviour of this age. The child develops a strong loyalty towards the group. Mental health includes social well-being and psychological

and emotional. It affects how we know, think, feel, perceive, and act. Its interpersonal relationships and decision-making are handled. Mental health is linked from childhood to adulthood. Mental health includes competence, autonomy, self-efficacy, subjective well-being, and interdependence. From positive psychology and well-being perspectives, mental health involves a person's ability to enjoy life: professional theories, subjective assessments, and cultural differences influence how "mental health" is defined. Irritability, thoughts of harming yourself or others, lack of energy, and insomnia are some early signs of mental health problems. For example, various mental health diseases, such as stroke, heart disease, and diabetes, can profoundly affect a person's mental illness. In particular, your way of thinking, behaviour and mood can be affected. Thus many factors contribute to mental health problems. Many people with mental health disorders consider their symptoms and signs to be a normal part of life. Avoid treatment out of fear and shame. If you experience mental health problems during your life, you can identify mental health conditions with appropriate treatment and support.

Linares et al. (2002) discuss the relationship between adult psychosocial competence and parenting style. For parents was positively related to psychosocial competence and self-esteem and neg associated with anti-social susceptibility. Pettit et al. (1991) found in a study that supports and warmth from parents are presumed to be social, emotional and moral competence through several mechanisms. 1) Children must embrace parental values when their relationship with their parents is mutually responsive. Children are also presumed to acquire positive relationships with parents p effective social orientations that generalize to others, and 3) Children acquire important information processing skills from parental interaction. It helps them to interact with their peer.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To determine the different levels of Psychosocial Competence in secondary school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District.
2. To find out the different levels of Mental Health in secondary school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District.
3. To assess the relationship between Psychosocial Competence and Mental Health of secondary school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is no significant difference in the level of psychosocial competence of secondary school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District, Telangana.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of Mental Health in secondary school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District, Telangana.
3. There is no relationship between psychosocial competence and Mental Health of secondary

school Indigenous students of Vikarabad District, Telangana.

METHOD

This study sticks to a descriptive research design in which the researcher describes a level of psychosocial competence in mental health in secondary school Indigenous students and finds the relationship between psychosocial competence and mental health. All school-going Indigenous students at Vikarabad District, Telangana, form the sample. The present study consisted of 40 samples of Indigenous students native to Vikarabad District. The Mental health of Indigenous students using standardized research tool by Arun Kumar and Sen Gupta, in 2007. Investigator developed the Psychosocial Competence Scale. On the scale total of 40 statements and five dimensions: i.e. Self Competence, Motivational Competence, Cognitive Competence, Emotional Competence and Social Competence. This is a five-point Likert Scale with 25 positive and 15 negative statements. As per the Investigator, the reliability is 0.833. Basic data were collected from Vikarabad District.

PROCEDURE:

Procedure As the present study was planned to investigate, the participants for the study were selected on a stratified random basis. At first, the investigators of the present study sought the cooperation of the principals of the TTWREIS schools and TTAS School students. Afterwards, the researcher approached the school participants and requested them to complete the questionnaires. Informed consent was taken from each participant. The instructions regarding both scales were given before they filled out the questionnaires. Their doubts were cleared before or during while they responded to the questionnaires.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES:

Finally, the tests were scored manually, and the data collected was recorded on excel sheets, which were later analyzed using SPSS. It requires collecting and searching every data sample in a set of items from which samples can be drawn. To draw comparisons and provide meaning to the study, the following statistical techniques were used to describe and interpret the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Everyone should understand the universality of mental health problems in the Indigenous adolescent peoples. It helps the school, family & mental health policy prevent mental health problems and take appropriate measures to promote emotional health and positive mental health. This current study's main variable for psychosocial competence & mental health research shows that secondary school Indigenous students had moderate levels of psychosocial competence & low levels of mental health. Along with this, the inter correlation matrix discovery show a significant effect between psychosocial competence & mental health variables.

This study revealed that 5.12 per cent of tribal students

have emotional symptoms, and 9.61 per cent of tribal students have behavioural problems. Hyperactivity among students and 1.4 per cent of tribal students have significant peer problems. Thus, the present study's findings suggest that mental health level is derelict & taking misunderstood in the adolescent students of the tribal community. Everyone should understand the ubiquity of mental health problems in Indigenous adolescent students. It helps the school, family & mental health strategy prevent mental health problems and take appropriate measures to promote positive emotional health.

CONCLUSION

Less than half of secondary school students, 48 per cent, have average levels of psychosocial competence. The study found that more than 52 per cent of local students in secondary school had poor mental health. In addition, the inter-correlation matrix result showed a significant correlation between mental health variables and psychosocial competence. Thus, this study proves that when the level of psychosocial competence increases, positive mental health also increases. Therefore, there is a need for the government to conduct life skills education programs regularly to improve psychosocial competence among indigenous students at secondary school. The government should conduct mental health screening camps in schools three times a month to identify indigenous secondary school students' behaviour and various mental health problems. Similarly, the government should come forward to help them according to their needs.

REFERENCES

1. Ali, A., & Eqbal, S. (2012). Mental Health status of tribal adolescent. International conference, 5(4), 23-34.
2. Das, S. et al., (2016). Assessment of adolescent problems in tribal adolescent girls :a cross sectional study. International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health, 3(5), 1014-1019.
3. Gadatia, B. S., & Mohalik, R. (2016). Life skills Need Assessment Among Tribal Students at Secondary level. Asian Journal of Social Science & Humanities, 5(3), 12-23.
4. Gopal, V. & Ashok. A. (2012). Prevalence of Emotional and Behavioral Problems among Tribal and Non-tribal Adolescents. Journal of the Indian Academic of Applied Psychology, vol 38(issue 1), pp 63-67.
5. Patel, V. et al., (2007). Mental health of young people: a global public-health challenge. international Journal of the Lancet, 369(9569), 1302-1313.
6. Wynaden, D. (2010). There is no health without mental health: Are we educating Australian nurses to care for the health consumer of the 21st century? International Journal of Mental Health Nursing, 19, 203-209.
7. Yadav, U. N. et al., (2013). A Comparative study on self-esteem among tribal and non-tribal students in Udipi Taluk, Karnataka, India. Global Journal of medicine and public health, 2(5), 12-13.
8. Unicef. (2011). The state of the World's children 2011, Adolescence: An age of Opportunity. New York: Division Communication. UNICEF, 3 United Nations, New York, NY 10017, USA Census of India, (2011), UN World Population Prospects, 12th Revision.